

The Impact of the School Counselor in the Integration of Arab Students into Higher Education in Israel

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Abstract:- In Israel, school counseling was originally incorporated into the curriculum in the 1960s. The primary responsibilities of the school counselor in Israel are counseling, consultation, coordination, and execution of guidance programs (Nations, 2020). These responsibilities were directly taken from the rationale and purpose of the school counseling program as it was published in the 1960s by the "American School Counselling Association" and the "American Personnel and Guidance Association." Two decades after the program's inception, the first school counselors to be employed in the Arab educational system in Israel started to show up at the beginning of the 1980s. In the Israeli educational system today, the percentage of Arab school counselors employed is less than 4% of the more than 2500 total school counselors (Meyer & Bell, 2023).

School counselors impact how well Arab students are integrated into higher education. Interventions in higher education also aim to support and inform Arab students to help them make informed decisions regarding their personal, higher education integration, and social lives (Easterbrook & Hadden, 2020). Thus, this study aimed to ascertain whether the school counselor's function has any bearing on student success and to assist Arab students who wish to enroll in higher education in Israel. The study used a mixed-methods approach to find answers to the following questions: What specific role does the school counselor play in helping Arab students in Israel integrate into higher education? Also, is there any real impact on the role played by school counselors in the integration of Arab students into higher education? The study's findings revealed that students overwhelmingly agreed that the school counselor's contributions to integrating Arab students into higher education in Israel included higher education guidance and counseling, higher education career goal identification, the organization of higher education career days and conferences, and administration of the occupational interest inventory.

Additionally, Arab students asserted that the school counselor's roles affect their higher education career decisions. Additionally, there was a favorable relationship between the counselor's function and how it affected Arab students' college integration. To promote Arab students' absorption into higher education, it is advised that frequent intervention activities be offered.

Keywords:- School Counselor, Higher Education Students, Occupational Interest, Higher Education Choice, Higher Education Guidance, Arab Students, Israel.

I. INTRODUCTION

An apple of eye point to be taken and logged in the prologue of this paper, is the immense role of the school counselor in taking the leap of the in-need students and leverage them in a such dramatical turning point period of time of their ages; the after-school life, a sphere which still unripen and in shadows in Israel, whereas it shall answer where the river of these in-need students, in these hypersensitive times, goes and how it leads them with all it implies.

Whence, one of the Arab counselor's main objectives is to enable Arab students to transition into Israeli higher education seamlessly (Mizel, 2022). Furthermore, it is undeniable that the main services provided by guidance and counseling are higher education integration guidance and counseling, which helps students make career decisions; vocational guidance and counseling, which helps a person select and prepare for a career that is compatible with his interests and aptitudes, and personal and social guidance and counseling, which helps a person act appropriately to others (Suryadi, Hanifa, Sawitri, & Suryadi, 2018).

Supporting works on higher education integration shed light on how difficult it is for school counselors to adapt to the demands of a society that is rapidly changing in terms of its workplace's diversity (Gleason, 2020). The requirement for great work performance, which permeates every aspect of an individual's life since it affects every role we play, has led to changes in counseling needs especially in higher education integration, especially in Arab students. Due to this, the school counselor's duty has evolved to encompass more than just higher education placement assistance. Even while choosing the right career is of the utmost significance, career counseling now addresses a wide range of challenges, including mental health problems that limit career options, workplace changes, and matching workers' needs in a globalized, competitive economy. These problems and many others present a difficult situation for Arab school counselors trying to integrate Arab students into Israel's higher education system (Refaeli, Alnabilsy, & Sold, 2023).

Reese (2021) argues that guidance counselors should be psychologically trained professionals who can normally provide a wide range of practical services to parents, students, and instructors of all students. Thus, the school counselor is a crucial team member or a member of the educational leadership team that offers Arab student's helpful assistance. In a school counseling program, school counselors traditionally offer advice and counseling to students on academic, vocational, and career counseling (American School Counsellor's association-ASCA, 2018). On the other hand, school counselors in Israel do provide students with a

variety of higher education-related programs that are intended to help students plan their careers, make informed decisions, and select a career that will lead them into the right vocation so that students will enjoy their work (Astramovich, Hoskins, Gutierrez, & Bartlett, 2018). As a result, students receive extensive higher education counseling programs (interventions) that demand career and life plans through all levels of education and beyond, as well as school-to-work programs that concentrate on preparing students for the workforce through extensive internship activities in communities and organizations (Ngo, 2023). To support Arab students with information and guidance regarding higher education, academic, and career options, as well as to guide and prepare students for multiple roles within broad industry sectors from the transition from high school to workplace, college, or university is a critical path juncture (Badran, Baydoun, and Hillman 2019), it is important to provide higher education integration intervention activities in the classroom. Such actions will also make it possible to adapt to the quickly developing technology. As a result, more training and education are required to help students enter the majority of areas, which are more crucial and complicated than ever before, and enable them to make informed decisions (Haleem, Javaid, Qadri, & Suman, 2022).

To expand students' future higher education integration opportunities, guidance counsellors must actively promote broad-based higher education integration that focuses on the interests and skills of each student (Haddock, Cannon, & Grey, 2020). Most students need more accurate information about jobs and careers to base their interests on. As for the maturation of occupational interests, aptitudes, and qualities, work experiences are crucial (Rastogi, 2020). Arab students in Israel must be encouraged to pursue higher education through short-term job tryout experiences and job shadowing opportunities that entail recording preferences and performance.

In order to help students to choose short-term occupations that will lead to long-term career outcomes, the counsellor must provide information on the student's preferences for activities, work surroundings, emotional and monetary rewards, and supervision. Such precise performance data may help the student prepare for the shift by letting them know what kind of higher education, work experience, effort, and time frame will be needed to fulfil their career preferences (Reese, 2021).

Therefore, the counsellor's role(s) is to influence Arab students in Israel's incorporation into higher education. These activities can help students develop the maturity and decision-making skills they need to succeed in career development tasks (Herrity, 2023). They can also be intentional attempts to improve certain aspects of students' career development (Isaacson & Brown, 2019).

The career development interventions the counsellor can concentrate on include higher education guidance, career counselling, career information, career education, career development programs, and career coaching (Perera & Athanasou, 2020). The student will eventually acquire the required skills of being provided with such high-quality

facilities because all of these interventions aid people in developing self-awareness, occupational awareness, learning career decision-making skills, job search skills, coping and adjusting to job stress, problem-solving skills, and others (Gleason, 2020). Counsellors can help Arab students explore their higher education and job options and gain knowledge by doing this. According to Haleem, Javaid, Qadri, and Suman, (2022), school counsellors can support stronger family collaboration by collaborating closely with parents to improve family- school communication and by giving parents the knowledge and attitudes they need to support their students in making wise career decisions. Their parent's beliefs influence students. School counsellors can engage with students to address confidence, self-assurance, self-worth, and positive attitudes, according to Astramovich, Hoskins, Gutierrez, and Bartlett (2018). School counsellors can play a significant role in raising students' self-efficacy about their capacity to excel in higher-level course material and pursue careers in mathematics in collaboration with teachers and parents.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Krumboltz's Learning Theory of Careers Choice and Counselling*

Researchers and theories go into great detail about how career counselors work with important people to help students choose the careers of their lives. For instance, in 1996, Krumboltz created the Learning Theory of Careers Choice and Counseling (LTCC) as a manual for working school counselors interested in learning how to support Arab students' integration into Israeli higher education. When deciding on a higher education program in the modern world, students must contend with four fundamental patterns that Mitchell and Krumboltz (2021) highlighted. Career counselors must assist students in navigating these trends. Arab students must first broaden their interests and skill sets. Counselors should encourage Arab students in Israel to try new things rather than always steering them based on measured preferences that only reflect restricted prior experiences. Second, pupils must get ready for shifting job duties. As a result, Arab students may find it very stressful to learn new skills for the evolving labor market. This can be effectively remedied by introducing practical assistance.

As students continuously learn new skills, counselors have a part to play in assisting them in managing stress (Herrity, 2023). Thirdly, it's important to give Arab students the power to act. In other words, many factors that are important to decisions about higher education are frequently ignored in counseling (such as how a family will react if the student accepts a particular profession). This could result in zeteophobia or the fear of making decisions, or it might delay making decisions altogether (Mizel, 2022).

Counselors must be willing to work together to address these problems and offer helpful encouragement while clients explore their options. Fourth, school counselors in Israel must take on more responsibilities (Rastogi, 2020). This implies that personal counseling and higher education should be combined. Burnout, career changes, peer relationships, roadblocks to professional advancement, and the nature of the

job and how it affects other responsibilities in life are a few potential issues that the higher education practitioner should support.

III. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The mixed method approach, also known as triangulation, was used in the current study, which used a descriptive survey design (Creswell, 2018). Creswell, Plano Clark, Guttman, and Hanson (2019) state three problems must be considered when conducting a mixed-methods study. This covers integration, implementation, and prioritization. Priority describes which approach—qualitative or quantitative—receives greater attention in the investigation. Because quantitative research represents the main part of data collecting and analysis in the study, it was given priority in

this study above the qualitative method. The researcher first gathered and examined the quantitative (numeric) data in this case. This guided the collection and analyzing qualitative (text) data used to explain and further develop the quantitative findings. This strategy was chosen because, while the quantitative data and analysis that followed it gave a broad understanding of the research problem, the qualitative data and analysis that followed it refined and provided a detailed explanation for the statistical findings by deeply examining participants' perspectives (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2018; Creswell, 2019).

A. Population

The population for the study was 100 Arab students from higher education. Thus, the target population comprised 100 Arab Israeli higher education students.

Table 1: Population Distribution of the Study Schools

Name of University	Target Population
Tel Aviv University	25
Bar Ilan University	25
Ono Academic College	25
Tel-Hai Academic College	25
TOTAL	100

B. Sample

A sample size of 100 students was selected from Israeli higher education centers. The sample size was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's 1970 table of population and the appropriate sample size.

From the 100 students who responded to the questionnaire, twenty-five (25) students from each school, totaling one hundred (100), were chosen to answer the interview and questionnaire. The students for the interview and questionnaire were chosen using the homogeneous sampling technique. This sampling approach is used when

choosing to include individuals or locations in your study because they share a trait or set of characteristics (Creswell, 2018). The study's sample size was chosen using a proportional stratified sampling technique.

Since each school needed to be fairly represented and there were four distinct ones with diverse populations, proportional stratified sampling was employed to choose students. Proportional stratified sampling is more objective regarding representation than random sampling (Tryfos, 2019).

Table 2: Sample Selected from each University

Name of University/College	Accessible Population	Sample
Tel Aviv University	1000	25
Bar Ilan University	1000	25
Ono Academic College	1000	25
Tel-Hai Academic College	1000	25
TOTAL	4000	100

Source: fieldwork data, 2023

C. Sampling Procedure

Public and private universities were stratified among the schools for this study. To choose the four schools, a purposeful sample technique was used.

Simple random sampling was used to choose the respondents for the study from the schools, and they were then given a questionnaire to fill out. Twenty-five respondents to the questionnaire from each of the schools considered in the study were chosen for an interview for the qualitative component of the study. This number was selected because qualitative research requires a relatively lower number of respondents to comprehend the study's connected concerns thoroughly.

D. Data Collection Procedure

The impact of the school counselor on the integration of Arab students into higher education in Israel was the topic of a focus group discussion and questionnaire used to gather data for the study. A week after the questionnaire was sent, an in-depth focused group discussion and/or interview were conducted after a letter of introduction was used to introduce the researchers. 25 students from each participating school participated in a thorough discussion of the study's issue at various times and on various days. In order to support the results of the questionnaire, this was done to ask the respondents for useful information. The test was administered by the researcher directly.

E. Method of Data Analyses

Both quantitative and qualitative data were obtained from the study. In order to analyze the data, both quantitative and qualitative methodologies were used. The study questions were analyzed using means and standard deviations, and the hypothesis was analyzed using Spearman's correlation and multiple regression (quantitative data). Thematic analysis was the chosen method for examining the qualitative data. During the focus group discussion on the role of the school counselor in assisting Arab students in Israel's higher education, the interview was audio taped. The respondents' schools were assigned the following codes: P1, for school 1, P2, for school 2, P3, for school 3, and P4, for school 4. The 25 responses from each school were also given the code P1A, which stands for student "A" from school 1. P1A to P1E, therefore, refers to students A through E from school 1. By using the same methodology, P2A to P2E, P3A to P3E, and P4A to P4E, respectively, represent the individual respondents from schools 2, 3, and 4. All of this was done to ensure that the responders received the confidentiality and anonymity they had promised. The researcher used the participants' own words to support the study topic when extracting the themes for the qualitative analysis. As one would need to look at each case and infer meaning from it as well as look at a categorical aggregation from a collection of examples, this, according to Creswell (2003), will help bring up the relevant meaning. The two main analytic approaches were within-school (case) and cross-school (case) analysis, which was produced through a comprehensive and attentive reading and rereading of the transcribed interview. The following inquiries served as the researchers' guides throughout the process: How can college students plan their careers in order to select a desired and suitable career? What elements decide or have an impact on Arab students attending higher education institutions in Israel? What role does the school counselor play in helping Arab students in Israel transition to higher education? Aspects that didn't relate to or were unimportant to the study's goal were eliminated. This made it easier to spot recurring problems in the participant narrators' stories.

Amoah (2019, citing Creswell, 2018) stated in his work establishing a reflective, collaborative practices model for counselor development: the four components in the Israeli case that the within-case study informs the cross-case analysis. This made it possible for the researcher to thoroughly understand each participant's perspective on the phenomenon, which facilitated the discovery of standout patterns and sped up the cross-case analysis procedure (Nations, 2020).

The cross-case analysis was performed to analyze how consistently specific difficulties appear in the contributions of all cases. According to Powell and Marcus (2019), referent themes from the within-case analysis were used to determine how the categories for the cross-case analysis were similar and different. According to Amoah (2019, citing Moore, Carol, Anthony, and McLaughlin 2021), looking beyond what the within-case initially suggests is essential. This altered the researcher's thinking when themes and categories across the case were explored, which inspired cross-case analysis. In conclusion, the analysis aided the researchers in interpreting the data in a more transparent, logical way that helped them respond to their study questions. The impact of the school counselor on integrating Arab students into higher education in Israel emerged as a vital issue for the investigation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Findings from the research question Research Question: What is the impact of the school counselor in the integration of Arab students into higher education in Israel?

Preference was given to the respondents to indicate the impact of the school counselor on the integration of Arab students into higher education in Israel. The findings are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Means and Standard Deviations of the Impact of the School Counselor in the Integration of Arab Students into Higher Education in Israel.

Role of school counselor	Mean	Standard Dev.
Higher education guidance & counselling	3.75	1.243
Career goals identification	3.71	1.483
Information on future opportunities	3.70	1.500
Higher education decision making	3.48	1.653
Help in self-assessment	3.32	1.601
Higher education awareness day	3.20	1.606
Organized higher education field trips	3.11	1.253
Higher education interest inventory	3.08	1.583
Higher education conference	2.99	1.625
Personality and higher education aptitude test	2.73	1.648
Mean of Means	33.07	13.542

Source: Data from the field, 2023

The study found that, among other career intervention activities, higher education guidance and counselling, career goals identification, information on future career opportunities, higher education decision-making, help with

self-assessment, higher education awareness day, organized higher education field trips, higher education interest inventory, and higher education interest survey formed the impact of the school counsellor in assisting the integration of

Arab students in higher education.

According to Table 3's findings, of the ten (10) roles the school counsellor provided to the students, the majority of the roles (eight) significantly influenced the Arab students' higher education self-efficacy in Israel. With a mean of 3.75 and a standard deviation of 1.243, the responses from the field showed that the students felt that higher guidance & counselling was the intervention activity that benefited them the most in choosing a vocation among the counsellor's duties. The following steps include identifying career goals (mean=3.71; standard deviation=1.483), learning about potential career opportunities (mean=3.70; standard deviation=1.501), self-assessment (mean=3.32; standard deviation=1.601), higher education awareness day (mean=3.20; standard deviation=1.606), higher education field trips (mean=3.11; standard deviation=1.253), and occupational interest inventory (mean=3.08; standard deviation=1.583). According to the table, respondents were unsure of the counsellor's functions in helping them make the desired profession choice, including conducting higher education conferences (Mean=2.99; sd=1.625) and

administering personality and higher education aptitude tests (Mean=2.73; sd=1.648). It is implied that the school counsellor's role includes higher education guidance and counselling, career goal identification, information on future career opportunities, higher education decision-making, assistance with self-evaluation, organization of higher education field trips, occupational, interest inventory, higher education conferences, and administration of personality and higher education aptitude tests.

B. Outcome of the analysis of the Hypothesis

The main study hypothesis was:

- **Hypothesis:** *There is a significant relationship between the impact played by the school counselor in integrating Arab students into higher education in Israel.*

The concern of this hypothesis was to determine whether the school counselor's role can impact Arab students' integration into higher education. Spearman's rho Correlation was used to test the role of the counselor and higher education integration among Arab students in Israel.

Table 4: Spearman's Rho Correlation of the Impact of the school Counselor in the Integration of Arab Students into Higher Education in Israel

Categories		Higher Education Integration	Impact of Counselor
Impact of counselor	Correlation	.086	1.000
	Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.123	
	N	100	100
Higher education integration	Correlation	1.000	.086
	Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.123
	N	100	100

Source: Data from field, 2023

The Spearman's Rank Order Correlation was statistically used to test the null hypothesis that there is no meaningful association between the role played by the school counselor and Arab students' integration into higher education. The association between Arab students' integration into higher education and the function of school counselors was investigated using Spearman's Rank Order correlation. The table demonstrated a positive correlation—which was statistically insignificant ($r_s = 0.086$, $sig=.123$, $p>0.05$)—between the function of the school counselor and Arab students' absorption into higher education in Israel. In other words, although the relationship between the counselor's job and its impact on Arab students' integration into higher education in Israel is beneficial, it is not particularly strong. The implication is that the null hypothesis is rejected (since there is a positive correlation) even though the positive correlation is statistically not insignificant. Although the table indicates no influence, the alternative hypothesis that there is a correlation between the school counselor's role in impacting Arab students' assimilation into higher education in Israel is accepted. This supports Watters' (2010) study, which claimed that a student's success in higher education is strongly influenced by the counselor's ability to maintain their interest in them during their entire time in school. This implies, however, that the student will not be able to

successfully transition into higher school if the counselor does not utilize an intervention that keeps the student's attention.

The reason for the weak correlation may be that the students did not take the cancelling service seriously or that the school counselors did not provide the necessary higher education integration intervention services to maintain their interest in the higher education integration in question. Counselors may lack the tools necessary to improve their efforts to aid Arab students in integrating into higher education. Other studies by Reese (2021) revealed that students are unhappy with school guidance counselors' services. Reese discovered considerable differences in the counseling services students required and the ones they received, with career counseling being the most important.

The government, other education stakeholders, and parents should support the school counselor by providing the tools necessary to enhance his work and make it appealing to students so that they will take it seriously because there is a positive correlation and counseling can, therefore, have a positive effect on students' choice of career.

C. Findings from the qualitative analysis: The impact of the school counselor in the integration of Arab students into higher education in Israel

Data from the study's subject area suggested that the school counselor significantly impacted how well Arab students integrated into higher education. Career presentations, open days, conferences, and one-on-one career counseling were topics that came up frequently.

According to the statistics, the school counselor would call students whose performance was poor as part of their responsibility to review students' records, including their performance, and provide them with one-on-one assistance, which led to some of them choosing a vocation.

The responses that follow attest to them.

"I was struggling in IT. The school counselor then called, and we talked about it. I consented to perform General Arts information. I rose to the top of the general art class.

I chose to become a lawyer after he talked about the job options available to me as a student of public arts". - P3C

P3E said in stating his side of the story:

"I received a call from the school counselor, and we spoke about changing our plans because I am doing well in math. I consented to pick a course that included both economics and accounting. My academic performance was excellent. I decided to become a banker after the seminar on higher education."

Speaking along the same lines, P4C added:

"I lost my sense of direction, which prevented me from learning and even from routinely attending lessons. I was instructed to speak with the school counselor, who talked to me about my options for employment as a technical student. In order to become an engineer or a construction technician, I decided to study and excel in technical drawing and building science."

Differently, P4C argued that:

"I was a bad boy. However, my interaction with the school counselor resulted in a change in my attitude and behavior. Because I liked the lecturer who attended the higher education conference, I took my studies seriously and decided to become a lecturer. "

The study found that the school counselor's planning of job fairs and conferences did aid students in making career decisions. P3A makes the following reasoning in favor of this:

"The school counselor organized a program that included a bank manager, a doctor, a nurse, a police officer, a lecturer from the Ono university, and many others. They explained what they do, how they do it, and how we may emulate them. The nurse persuaded me. That is why I decided to pursue a career as a nurse....occasionally, the counselor invited the teachers to share their experiences with us and how delighted they are to produce outstanding men and

women for the country. I was motivated and decided to train those who could improve our society by becoming a teacher."

P2D added:

"We were given a speaker from Tel Aviv University to explain the prospects for further education available to students following school in various courses or subject areas. I could be serious, concentrate, and focus better on my technical course since I was better informed about my post-secondary work options"

The career day programs and seminars did not assist P4C in making his career decision. He said:

"Even though such programs 'opened my eyes' to understand the different aspects of work or career, I was not happy because it did not help me to choose my career because no architect or building engineer was brought to talk to us about their field of work."

According to the history of school counseling, counselors offer advice and counseling to students enrolled in a school counseling program on topics including higher education, vocation, and career (American School Counselor's Association-ASCA, 2019).

V. CONCLUSION

The counselor impacted Arab students' integration into higher education in Israel. However, the impact of the counselors' work on Arab students' assimilation into higher education was minimal. This may be due to a lack of enough resources, ineffective and inefficient follow-up, and improper counselor-parent consultation over the student's higher education integration choice as opposed to their ability and interest. This might be one of the reasons why some students did not choose the correct career path and ended up working as yogurt vendors in shops or joining the "rebel" group.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

For Arab students to make informed choices about higher education integration, it is advised that frequent intervention initiatives be set up. Moreover, a strong shout out must go to the Israeli Ministry of Education and governmental stakeholders to reincarnate and reinforce by all means the role of the school counselors as a pre-stage and foreteller of the students' futuristic careers.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Astramovich, R. L., Hoskins, W. J., Gutierrez, A. P., & Bartlett, K. A. (2018, October 15). Identifying Role Diffusion in School Counseling. 3(3).
- [2.] Badran, A., Baydoun, E., & Hillman, J. R. (2019). Major Challenges Facing Higher Education in the Arab World: Quality Assurance and Relevance . Switzerland : Springer.
- [3.] Easterbrook, M., & Hadden, I. (2020, October 8). Tackling Educational Inequalities with Social Psychology: Identities, Contexts, and Interventions. 15(1), 180-236. doi:https://doi.org/10.1111/sipr.12070.

- [4.] Gleason, N. W. (2020, January 7). Conclusion: Strategic Leadership for Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education.
- [5.] Haddock, L., Cannon, K., & Grey, E. (2020). A Comparative Analysis of Traditional and Online Counselor Training Program Delivery and Instruction. Springer .
- [6.] Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., & Suman, R. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. 3, 275-285. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susoc.2022.05.004>
- [7.] Herrity, J. (2023, March 29). 7 Ways To Improve Your Personal Development Skills.
- [8.] Meyer, K., & Bell, E. (2023, February 9). The school counselor staffing landscape: Policies and practice. Retrieved from <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/brown-center-chalkboard/2023/02/09/the-school-counselor-staffing-landscape-policies-and-practice/>
- [9.] Mizel, O. (2022, November 11). Perspective Chapter: Visible or Invisible? Arab Students in the Israeli Academic World. doi:DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.110077
- [10.] Nations, U. (2020). Global Education Monitoring Report 2020: Inclusion and Education - All Means All. United Kingdom.
- [11.] United Kingdom.
- [12.] Ngo, C. (2023, April 20). Counseling Careers. Retrieved from <https://www.bestcolleges.com/careers/counseling/>
- [13.] Perera, H. N., & Athanasou, J. A. (2020). International Handbook of Career Guidance. Germany: Springer International Publishing.
- [14.] Rastogi, A. (2020, April 6). Need and Importance of Career Guidance.
- [15.] Reese, D. M. (2021, March 12). School Counselor Preparation to Support Inclusivity, Equity and Access for Students of Color With Disabilities. 6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2021.588528>
- [16.] Refaeli, T., Alnabilsy, R., & Sold, A. (2023, February 14). Barriers to Post-Secondary Education among Young Arab-Bedouin Women in Israel. 42(3), 350-368. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/13602004.2023.2176069>
- [17.] Suryadi, H., Hanifa, F., Sawitri, D., & Suryadi, B. (2018, June). The Effect of Counselor Role in Vocational Guidance Services on Career The Effect of Counselor Role in Vocational Guidance Services on Career Orientation of Senior Secondary School Students.